

Potentiometric Studies on the Binding of Beryllium, Strontium, Thorium, and Magnesium by Gelatin

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Potentiometric studies on the binding of beryllium, strontium magnesium, and thorium by gelatin, carried out at the total ionic strength of 0.15, provide evidence for the binding of Be^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , and Th^{4+} through the carboxyl groups of the protein; no such information is available in the case of magnesium.

The metal complexes of many biochemically important compounds, like amino-acid, simple peptides, etc., have been extensively investigated by Albert¹ and Mork², employing Bjerrum's method³. The *pH*-metric method, though of little value for investigating the complexes of proteins, may be usefully employed to determine the nature of metal-ion binding to proteins as is evident from the work of Scatchard and Black⁴, Steinhardt *et al.*⁵, and Tanford and Epstein⁶. But such studies are limited to simple proteins like serum albumin and insulin and no attempt has yet been made to investigate *pH*-metrically the behaviour of complex proteins towards metal ions. The present communication deals with the potentiometric studies on the interaction of beryllium, strontium, thorium, and magnesium with gelatin.

EXPERIMENTAL

A 4% gelatin solution was prepared by dissolving Difco gelatin in double distilled water. The *pH* of the solution was found to be 6.50.

Beryllium nitrate, strontium nitrate (both E. Merck), thorium nitrate (B. D. H.), magnesium sulphate (A.R.), and hydrochloric acid (A.R) were used for preparing their respective solutions. The *pH*s of the metal salt solutions were adjusted to 1.7 by addition of 0.1*N*-HCl. Carbonate-free KOH solution was prepared and its strength determined potentiometrically by titrating against 0.05*M* potassium hydrogen sulphate.

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1. *Biochem. J.*, 1950, 47, 531; 1952, 50, 600.

2. *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1951, 47, 292; 1951, 47, 297.

3. "Metal Ammine Formation in Aqueous Solution", Haase and Son, Copenhagen, 1957.

4. *J. Phys. Coll. Chem.*, 1944, 53, 89.

5. *J. Res. Nat. Bur. Standards*, 1941, 26, 293; *Ann. N. Y. Acad. Sci.*, 1941, 41, 287.

6. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 2163, 2170.

7. Kolthoff and Sandell, "Textbook of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 3rd ed., Macmillan Co., New York, N. Y., 1952, p. 526.

Procedure.—The experimental procedure was the same as reported earlier⁸. Measurements of *pH* were carried out with a Beckman *pH*-meter, Model G. The ionic strength in different mixtures was maintained at 0.15 by adding a requisite amount of KCl solution. Precipitation of Be²⁺, Mg²⁺, and Th⁴⁺ occurred at *pH* 4.8, 10.0, and 4.0 respectively. Strontium, however, did not undergo precipitation even beyond *pH* 11.0. The *pH* for the onset of precipitation increased (*pH* 5.5, 10.42 and 6.42) in presence of the protein, indicating the binding of the metal ions by the active groups of the proteins. In no case denaturation and salting out effect were observed.

The amount of hydrogen ion bound to the protein, C_p , was determined by the relationship: $C_p = C_0(C_B + C_F)$, where C_0 is the total concentration of the hydrogen ions, C_F , the concentration of free hydrogen ions, and C_B , that reacting with the equivalent amount of base. The competition between the hydrogen ions and the metal ions for the protein resulted in the decrease of C_p values. The results are recorded in Table I (except for Mg where the curve lies above the H⁺-titration curve, Fig. 1). Experiments were repeated several times to ensure accuracy of *pH* measurements.

TABLE I

Protein conc. = 0.53%. $C_0 = 47.71 \times 10^{-3}M$. Ionic strength = 0.15. Conc. of Be²⁺, Sr²⁺, Mg²⁺, and Th⁴⁺ were 0.002M each.

*KOH added.	HCl	Values of C_p in moles/litre $\times 10^3$.			
		Be.	Sr.	Tb.	
0.0	47.08	45.81	45.72	45.89	
8.0	39.42	39.36	39.36	39.36	
9.0	38.65	38.53	38.55	38.55	
9.5	38.20	38.11	38.11	38.13	
10.0	37.71	37.61	37.61	37.63	
11.0	..	36.68	36.67	36.69	
12.0	..	35.67	35.69	35.71	
13.0	..	34.68	34.70	..	
13.5	..	34.19	34.20	..	
14.0	..	33.70	33.61	..	

*In moles/litre $\times 10^3$.

DISCUSSION

Fig. 1. shows that the titration curves for thorium, strontium, and beryllium lie well below that for HCl solution of the same *pH* (curve B). It may therefore be concluded that the ions of these metals compete with hydrogen ions in their reaction with gelatin. Since in the *pH* range 3.5-5.0, only carboxyl groups can offer principal sites for metal-ion binding, evidently these groups are involved primarily in the reactions of the metal ions under investigation. The extent to which these ions can compete with hydrogen ions is self-evident from the nature of the curves. The position of curve E, lying far below A, B, and C, followed by D for strontium, indicate that beryllium ions are the most effective

8. Salahuddin and Malik, this *Journal*, 1962, 39, 693, 699; Malik and Salahuddin, *J. Electroanal. Chem.* 1962, 5, 68, 147.

in bringing about the shift in pH . The curve for thorium (C) exhibits an insignificantly small flat portion, pointing towards a much lesser binding of thorium by the carboxyl groups of gelatin.

FIG. 1 Potentiometric titration in presence of gelatin (ionic strength = 0.15).

and hydrogen ion cannot be visualised in the pH range⁹, 9.6 to 11.0 (Fig. 1, curve B), pH -metric studies would be of little value in ascertaining the binding of magnesium to gelatin.

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